

GLH (Table 1). By 35 DT, the rates did not significantly differ from each other.

RTV was 45-65% at 56 DT and increased to 68-88% by 63 DT. All insecticide rates tested kept GLH below the economic injury level of 25 insects/hill, but did not prevent RTV.

At Lanrang, GLH was found 48-56 insects/40 hills at 18 DT (Table 2). All insecticide rates tested were ineffective at 25 and 32 DT, but were effective at 39 DT. By 53 DT, treatments were not significantly different from each other. Severe RTV infection was found at 60 DT. All treatments were ineffective in

Table 2. GLH population and RTV incidence at Lanrang, Indonesia, 1986.

Buprofezin concentration (g (ml)/ha)	Formulation	GLH ^a (no./40 hills)		Tungro incidence (%) 60 DT
		25 DT	46 DT	
250	10 WP	44.7 ab	19.7 ab	99
500	10 WP	30.2 ab	15.5 a	96
1000	10 WP	39.5 ab	17.5 a	98
250	400 EC	40.7 ab	17.5 a	98
500	400 EC	51.2 b	20.7 ab	97
1000	400 EC	28.0 a	17.7 a	95
0 (control)	—	74.5 c	26.7 b	99

^aIn a column, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P 0.05.

suppressing RTV. Buprofezin is slow to control GLH populations because it acts

only during molting. The delay allows RTV to be transmitted. □

Knockdown of green leafhopper (GLH) by six insecticides

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Some insecticides that control GLH effectively do not always prevent tungro (RTV) infection. This is probably due to slow knockdown, as GLH can transmit RTV before it dies. Using foliar spray and contact toxicity tests, we evaluated four pyrethroids, one carbamate, and one organophosphate in the laboratory for quick knockdown.

In the foliar spray test, 30-d-old potted seedlings of highly susceptible TNI were cleaned, placed on an electrically rotating table, and uniformly sprayed with insecticide, using an Arthur Thomas sprayer. Spray rates were 0.005, 0.15, and 0.01% ai. Control plants were sprayed with distilled water.

Ten minutes after treatment (MAT), the mylar film-caged plants were infested with 20 GLH adults. Knockdown mortalities were recorded up to 24 h after insect release.

In the contact toxicity test, 20 GLH adults were collected from rearing cages, anaesthetized with CO₂ gas for 10 s, and transferred onto petri dishes lined with filter paper. The dishes were placed at the bottom of a Potter's spray tower and sprayed with insecticide solution.

Treated adults were transferred to 15-d-old untreated TNI seedlings. Mortality was recorded to 60 MAT.

With foliar spraying, adult mortalities

Table 1. Effect of foliar spraying of 6 insecticides on *N. virescens* adults. IIRRI insectary, 1986.

Insecticide ^a	Rate (% ai)	Adult female mortality (%) at indicated time after release ^b		
		1 h	3 h	24 h
Alphamethrin	0.01	77 c	79 b	90 b
Cypermethrin	0.01	100 a	100 a	100 a
Ethoproxyfen	0.01	100 a	100 a	100 a
MIPC	0.15	98 b	100 a	100 a
Monocrotophos	0.15	79 c	100 a	100 a
Deltamethrin	0.005	100 a	100 a	100 a
Control	—	0 d	0 c	0 c

^aSpray volume based on 500 liters water/ha. ^bAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Effect of contact spray of 6 insecticides on *N. virescens* adults. IIRRI insectary, 1986.

Insecticide ^a	Rate (% ai)	Adult female mortality (%) at indicated time after treatment ^b			
		5 min	10 min	20 min	60 min
Alphamethrin	0.01	2 cd	4 c	15 c	16 c
Cypermethrin	0.01	70 a	92 a	100 a	100 a
Ethoproxyfen	0.01	15 b	21 b	36 b	49 b
MIPC	0.15	2 cd	4 c	0 d	19 c
Monocrotophos	0.15	5 cd	4 c	2 d	2 de
Deltamethrin	0.005	79 a	95 a	100 a	100 a
Control	—	0 d	0 c	0	0 e

^aSpray volume based on 500 liters water/ha. ^bAv of 4 replications, 20 GLH/replication. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

were significantly high with all 6 insecticides 1 h after release (Table 1). With direct spraying, the synthetic

pyrethroids deltamethrin and cypermethrin showed significantly higher knockdown 5 MAT (Table 2).

Effect of synthetic pyrethroid insecticides on green leafhopper (GLH) and tungro (RTV)

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We evaluated 4 synthetic pyrethroids — ethoproxyfen (0.1 kg ai/ ha), cypermethrin (0.05 kg ai/ ha), alphamethrin, and deltamethrin (0.0125 kg ai/ ha) — for *Nephotettix virescens* GLH and

RTV control in the field in 1984 dry season (DS). Wet seedbeds of highly susceptible TN1 and susceptible IR22 were covered with nylon mesh immediately after sowing to protect seedlings from GLH. Starting 1 d after transplanting (DT), 8 insecticide applications were made at weekly intervals. Disease incidence was recorded at 60 DT.

The same materials and methods were used in a 1985 wet season (WS) trial, but insecticide applications were reduced to five.

In the 1984 DS, RTV infection in plots treated with any of the pyrethroids was significantly lower than in the untreated control. Cypermethrin gave the lowest RTV incidence (see table).

RTV control by 4 synthetic pyrethroids on 2 susceptible rices at IRR, 1984-85.

Insecticide ^a	Formulation	RTV ^b (% infected hills) at 60 DT			
		1984 DS		1985 WS	
		IR22	TN1	IR22	TN1
Cypermethrin	5 EC	7.8 a	9.6 a	2.5 a	29.6 ab
Ethoproxyfen	20 EC	7.8 a	21.7 abc	2.6 a	22.9 a
Alphamethrin	10 EC	11.5 ab	21.3 abc	3.9 ab	39.4 ab
Deltamethrin	2.5 EC	14.4 ab	29.7 bc	3.3 ab	24.1 a
Control		30.3 c	81.9 d	5.3 b	43.4 b

^aInsecticide was applied at 1, 8, 15, 22, 29, 36, 43, and 50 DT in the 1984 DS and at 1, 20, 34, 49, and 63 DT in the 1985 WS. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

In the 1985 WS, RTV infection was significantly lower on IR22 treated with ethoproxyfen and cypermethrin and on TN1 treated with ethoproxyfen and deltamethrin.

The degree of control with the synthetic pyrethroids improved with more frequent applications early in crop growth. On susceptible varieties, control of RTV by insecticides was low. □

Chemical control of rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzivora*

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A 2-yr study (1982-83) investigated chemical control of GM on irrigated rice in southwestern Burkina Faso, where the pest is prevalent.

Carbofuran at 1.2 kg ai/ha and deltamethrin at 2.5 g ai/ha in a randomized block design with 5 treatments and 5 replications were evaluated. Plot size was 32 rows of 20 hills. Silvershoots at 45, 60, and 75 d after transplanting were counted on 4 rows/plot. Yield was estimated from 20 rows/plot.

Chemical control of rice GM^a. Burkina Faso, 1982-83.

Chemical applied at indicated time					Damage (% silvershoots) 75 DT	Yield (t/ha)
0 DT	15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT		
1982						
-	-	-	-	-	26 b	5.39 b
Carbofuran	-	-	Deltamethrin	-	23 ab	6.31 a
Carbofuran	-	-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	18 ab	7.31 a
-	Deltamethrin	-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	20 ab	6.40 a
Carbofuran	-	Carbofuran	-	Carbofuran	16 a	6.68 a
1983						
-	-	-	-	-	21 bc	4.91 b
Carbofuran	-	-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	16 ab	6.46 a
Carbofuran	-	-	Carbofuran	-	11 a	6.91 a
-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	Carbofuran	-	11 a	6.12 a
-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	11 a	5.91 a

^aDT = days after transplanting. In a column and in a year, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Treatments that included at least one application of carbofuran were effective

(see table). Yields were 1-2 t/ha higher than without treatment. □

Pest Control and Management

WEEDS

Herbicides to control weeds in transplanted rice

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In southeastern Rajasthan, labor for

manual weeding is scarce and expensive. I evaluated herbicides in kharif seasons 1984-85.

Seven herbicides at 2 rates of application were compared with hand weeding 20 and 40 d after transplanting (DT) and an unweeded check. The

experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

Weed seed (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) was broadcast at 5 kg/ha immediately after transplanting. Herbicides were applied 6 DT.